

MANAGEMENT UPGRADATION IN LITERARY EXALTATION

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Cite This Article: Dr. V. Kumaran, "Management Upgradation in Literary Exaltation", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 195-196, 2017.

It is ascribed that both sexes, male and female, cannot move in their own different trajectories on different directions. Literature reflects that men and women are embodied together in the natural organization. The psychological dimensions of the two are bound together in the form of family which allows many things to occur in the universe and also through which the universe gets meaning through their occurrence. The constellation of the social set up, customs, culture, tradition and family, are formed so as to bring peace in the society and fundamental rights for both sexes are prepared methodically for their well beings. Language contribution seems to be a prime concern for the social integration.

Language as well as its various genres remains as a moral code which tends to perceive mankind's attitudes, feelings and beliefs about his life runs and its various means. The brilliance of language determines and relates occupational responsibilities such as communication, goal-setting, hard-working, accountability, task completion, autonomy, reliability, support, honesty, effort, timeliness, determination, leadership, volunteerism and dedication. Stable communicative modes harness positive and productive approach in the work force. A healthy communication establishes management as well as technical promotions and rapports in between employers and the employees towards progression with ethical values. Work ethic, a complex and individualistic subject, in work spot becomes visible which is imperative that when one puts careful consideration into his or her own work philosophy so that he can best express himself through valuable language when the need arises.

A matrix of overwhelming skepticism, tardiness, antagonism gives an impression of a massive corrosion of democracy and career integrity and they undermine human and materialistic values. An effective language played in different communicative segments as individual presentation, group discussion, board meetings and documentations stems out such corrosion and cultivates the nobility of love and promises towards promoting work ethical values. A language set up is based on a strong cultural ground and it is a string tagging life and profession together. When it loses its tenderness and strength its effects create negative patterns in all grounds of human life. The following genre of W.B. Yeats "The Second Coming" plays the readers' heart to feel bridging the social and work ethics together with its tender cadence such as:

Turning and turning in the widening gyre
The falcon cannot hear the falconer;
Things fall apart; the centre cannot hold;
Mere anarchy is loosed upon the world,
The blood-dimmed tide is loosed, and everywhere
The ceremony of innocence is drowned;

Civic virtue is a high merit or a standard underpinning of honest behavior in rapport establishment to a citizen's involvement in society. An individual can implement civic virtue by voting, volunteering, group organization, or attending and creating brain transforming campaign and other life evolutionary phases. All kinds of literature witness that such evolutionary processes get growing through only stable language set up from bygone age to modern age. Literary fictions, social literature, architectural literature, medical literature and technical literature are getting a vital hot spot in the universal history.

Global organizations errands the candidates with language particularly English as a second language because the candidates can enhance themselves in the linking factor between the regional offences and make certain a good communicative flow. It means as an individual can get exposure to projects that he could normally be involved in, as he may be required to translate and then add auxiliary contributions. The editor of "The HRIDS World" shares of trade and language in his 'How Your Knowledge of English Can Influence Your Career Prospects' as:

How long will English be the trade language? Probably as long as all of us live, it will be. China has adapted English as their second language and is mandatory in their schools. Will it be long before there will be more English spoken by Chinese than there are in the world? Will most everyone be speaking two languages? Don't know, but I do know their embracing of the English language will result in English being around for a very long time. (<http://www.thehrisworld.com/how-english-can-influence-your-career/>)

Technology gets metamorphosed and overwhelmed through the hi-tech process of brain transformation from one nation to another nation. English remains mandatory if a technical explorer wishes to go abroad on assignments or for work. He is occurred to fulfill the technical concomitant successfully through various kinds of

communication by means of his rational techno exposure. He is a deciding authority of such commitment and he uses to select some choice based contradictory dealings. Such candidate is able to defy the commitment with his own language exposure. Self-development by learning offers him backhand support for his triumphed choice. Probity, courage, honour, integrity, characteristic efficiency, compliance and competency are encapsulated with moral autonomy averts policy volatility and moral dilemma.

When well learned technician applies all such aspects into his work, the industry and its outputs get exuberance. English is the fountain head of all the face lifting technical evolutions in the modern days. Alexander Pope's "The Essays of Criticism" sketches the value of great worker

O fool! to think God hates the worthy mind,
The lover and the love of humankind,
Whose life is healthful, and whose conscience clear,
Because he wants a thousand pounds a year.
Honour and shame from no condition rise;
Act well your part: there all the honour lies.

(<http://theotherpages.org/poems/pope-e4.html>)

Empathy is a natural practice of perceiving another person's state. We keep ourselves in their shoes. Co-operation creates good social bond and strengthens a stable professional society. Empathy and cooperation are inseparable rudimentary aspects of the functionality of an industry which establish a peaceful environment in the work spot. It progresses the industrial outputs in all segments of industry. When empathy and co-operation are saddled in every aspect of the innovative finding and the problem solving sessions like one and one meeting, group discussion, board meeting and conference, the industrial status gets ripened. The technical fruition gets perfection when the rapport is maintained meaningfully in between employers and employees by means of effective language structure. When a language is tagged in short sentence with sharp sense enhances the communication among the people. Love and rational perception are inevitable for a technical growth. In literature, Coleridge's "The Rime of the Ancient Mariner" stands for a personification of Love and exploration. It focuses, with its own outstanding literary mirth, the effect of loss of empathy in an exploration.

Day after day, day after day,
We stuck, nor breath nor motion;
As idle as a painted ship
Upon a painted ocean.
Water, water, everywhere,
And all the boards did shrink;
Water, water, everywhere,
Nor any drop to drink.

To get a job and get a career exist as integrated two bipolar things. Getting a job seems to be a fulcrum for smoothened survival but a career signifies that there is an opulent opportunities for progression which leads to do new things and take on supplementary incumbents. A career could make us travel to various countries. All our endeavors and involvements get rejuvenated by only language and its various growths utilization. An action without interest and involvement never get perfection. Shakespeare's "Hamlet" proves its own literary uniqueness as 'My words fly up, my thoughts remain below: words without thoughts never to heaven go.'

Thoughtful verses would give perfection in all kinds of documentations and would expand meaningful conscience. Well planed language construction in listening, speaking, reading, and writing can only generate any organization without any strategic vacillation. Language seems, indeed, to be an eye opener of all the layers of human evolution and his needs.

References:

1. The Works of William Shakespeare, Ward, Lock & Co., Limited, London and Melbourne.
2. English Poetry: A Kaleidoscope. University Press (India) Ltd., Hyderabad A: 2001. Print.
3. <http://www.thehrisworld.com/how-english-can-influence-your-career>
4. <http://theotherpages.org/poems/pope-e4.html>